

Natural Language Processing and Voice Recognition for Geolocation and Geospatial Visualization in Notebook Environment

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Abstract

This study develops an audio-based geolocation application using voice recognition within Google Colaboratory. Advances in Natural Language Processing (NLP) have significantly impacted various fields, including virtual assistants and geospatial applications. The research aims to capture voice commands, process audio to extract location information, and display geospatial data on an interactive map. The application uses the Web Speech API for real-time voice recognition and the geopy library for geocoding. Methodology includes capturing high-quality audio via JavaScript, processing with Python libraries ffmpeg and librosa, and using the SpeechRecognition library for transcription. The system's multilingual speech recognition enhances accessibility and usability. Results confirm the feasibility of voice-command geolocation in Google Colaboratory. Future research should enhance voice interaction capabilities, explore geolocation methods like bounding boxes, and reduce dependence on JavaScript and Flask. Improving peripheral device requirements could further enhance system accuracy and user experience.

1. Introduction

New innovations are being incorporated into everyday tools, affecting a variety of fields, as a result of emerging technologies such as voice recognition and natural language processing (NLP). These technologies enable natural interaction between humans and machines, thus allowing the use of complex technologies without the need for traditional interfaces (Austerjost et al., 2018). They have been implemented across several sectors, including virtual assistants, customer service systems, and, more recently, geospatial applications (Mahmoudi; Camboim; Brovelli, 2023a, 2023b).

In geoinformatics, these advances are crucial for improving the visualization of maps and geospatial data. Traditional cartography relied heavily on static representations of spatial data, but new technologies enable the creation of interactive and dynamic maps that can be manipulated in real-time (Craglia et al., 2012). Online mapping applications like OpenStreetMap, along with open geospatial data, have democratized spatial information by allowing public participation in its creation and maintenance (Haklay, 2010). This democratization movement is essential as it facilitates broader participation in the collection and use of geospatial data, promoting higher levels of inclusion and accessibility.

Geolocation is essential in several contemporary applications, such as navigation, emergency services, location-based marketing, and logistics management (Huang and Gartner, 2018; Jang and Lee, 2018). The ability to identify the exact whereabouts of a device or person at any given moment has revolutionized our interactions with the surrounding environment (Huang and Gartner, 2018; Cheema, 2018). However, the process of obtaining precise geographic coordinates using traditional methods encounters several obstacles. Fluctuation in GPS signal strength, especially in densely populated metropolitan areas, and the complexity of user interfaces in digital mapping tools are substantial challenges (Huang et al., 2020). Moreover, the requirement of proficient technical skills to effectively engage with geographic data limits the accessibility of these technologies to less experienced individuals (Jang and Lee, 2018; Huang and Gartner, 2018). Previous studies demonstrate that multimodal interfaces, which

combine voice, gestures, and touch, can significantly reduce the complexity of Geographic Information System (GIS) interfaces (Fuhrmann et al., 2005; Oviatt, 1996). The integration of voice recognition technology with mapping applications allows users to interact with map data and access information in a more natural and intuitive way, without the need for complex user interfaces or manual input (Austerjost et al., 2018).

1.1 Objectives

The main objective of this study is to develop a geolocation application that utilizes voice recognition technology to enable verbal interaction with geospatial data in the Google Colaboratory environment. This application will be designed to capture voice commands from users, process the audio to extract location information, and display the corresponding geographic data on an interactive map. This study seeks to answer the research question: "Is it possible to develop a voice command application for geolocation and visualization of geospatial data within the Google Colaboratory environment?"

By exploring these questions, the study will contribute to the understanding of the potential of voice recognition technologies in geospatial applications, offering valuable insights for the development of more accessible and efficient tools for interacting with geographic data. The research aligns with the "Digital Earth" vision, which emphasizes the importance of making geospatial data accessible and usable by a broad spectrum of users (Craglia et al., 2012). Additionally, implementing a voice assistant for geospatial data visualization represents a significant advancement in the field, addressing the need for more user-friendly and accessible geospatial tools (Mahmoudi; Camboim; Brovelli, 2023a, 2023b; Cai et al., 2005).

2. Materials and Methods

Google Colab is a free platform that provides access to powerful hardware such as GPUs and TPUs, which is essential for Machine Learning and Deep Learning tasks, facilitating prototyping and experimentation without additional configuration (Bisong, 2019; Sharma et al., 2020). According to its creators, its goal is to advance education and research in Machine Learning. It also enables effective collaboration among

teams by allowing simultaneous sharing and editing of notebooks via Google Drive (Bisong, 2019). Studies show that Colab offers competitive performance compared to other platforms, making it a viable and cost-effective option for research and development in artificial intelligence (Carneiro et al., 2018). To aid understanding, this section is divided into six subchapters, namely: Audio Data Acquisition, Audio Processing, Speech Recognition, Geocoding, Visualization, and Interface Development, which will be detailed below. The complete code and additional information can be found on this [GitHub page](#).

2.1 Audio Data Acquisition

Capturing audio directly from the browser is a fundamental step in the audio-based geolocation process, as it provides the necessary input for the entire subsequent processing flow. The capture is done using the Web Speech API in JavaScript, which allows real-time speech recognition and integrates with the MediaDevices API to access the user's microphone. This approach provides an interface for high-quality audio recording, essential for the accuracy of speech recognition and geocoding.

2.1.1 Web Speech API and MediaDevices API

The Web Speech API is a technology that enables speech recognition directly in the browser. It has two main components: SpeechRecognition, which converts speech into text, and SpeechSynthesis, which converts text into speech. For this project, SpeechRecognition was used to capture and transcribe voice commands (Natal, Shires and Jägenstedt, 2020; Adorf, 2013). The MediaDevices API, on the other hand, provides access to media devices, such as microphones and cameras, allowing audio and video capture directly from the user's hardware (Marr, 2018).

2.1.2 Audio Capture Implementation

Audio capture is carried out through a JavaScript interface that interacts with the aforementioned APIs. During audio capture, the system responds to specific voice commands, such as "Claudia" to start recording and "Robinson" to stop. This control method is essential to ensure a simple and effective interaction with the system, eliminating the need for complex user interfaces. The choice of these commands aims to enhance usability, allowing users to intuitively control the recording (Goodwin, 2017).

By implementing this approach, the system provides a seamless user experience, where voice commands can be issued naturally without the need for manual input. This setup is particularly useful in geospatial applications, where ease of use and minimal distraction are critical for users who need to focus on real-time data analysis or navigation tasks. The use of these predefined keywords simplifies the interaction while maintaining accuracy and control over the system's behavior.

The choice of ffmpeg is based on its robust multimedia processing capabilities, which include converting between different audio and video formats. It is effective for handling multimedia files because of its ability to work with a wide variety of codecs and formats (Bellard, 2019).

After conversion, the audio in wav format is processed using the Librosa library. Librosa is a Python-based audio analysis library designed to provide a user-friendly interface for common audio processing tasks such as file loading, resampling, and feature extraction. It simplifies the workflow for handling complex audio data, making it ideal for tasks like speech recognition and geolocation.

2.2 Audio Processing

2.2.1 Audio Capture Implementation

Audio format conversion is performed to ensure that the captured audio is in a format that allows for efficient and accurate processing. The webm format, while efficient for data storage and transmission, is not widely supported by audio processing libraries. Therefore, conversion to the wav format is necessary. ffmpeg is used for this conversion. This tool is a comprehensive framework for recording, converting, and streaming audio and video.

2.2.2 Audio Processing with Librosa

The Librosa library is used for processing the converted audio. Librosa offers a range of functionalities for audio signal analysis and manipulation, including:

- a) Loading Audio Files: Allows loading audio files in various formats, facilitating the reading and manipulation of audio data.
- b) Resampling: Adjusts the audio sampling rate, ensuring that the audio signal is at the appropriate rate for subsequent processing.
- c) Feature Extraction: Extracts important information from the audio signal, such as spectrograms, MFCCs (Mel-frequency cepstral coefficients), among others.

In this step, the audio is loaded in wav format, and the original sampling rate is preserved (`sr=None`). The use of Librosa simplifies the preparation of the audio for the speech recognition stage, allowing the extraction of relevant features that are essential for the accurate transcription of the audio.

2.2.3 Resampling

Resampling is an important step in audio processing, especially when dealing with signals captured at different sampling rates. Librosa allows adjusting the audio sampling rate to a standard rate, ensuring that subsequent processing is consistent. This process is crucial for ensuring the quality and accuracy of speech recognition, as inconsistent sampling rates can lead to errors in transcription (Smith, 2011).

2.2.4 Feature Extraction

Feature extraction is the stage where relevant information is extracted from the audio signal to be used in speech recognition. Librosa provides several functions for feature extraction, such as spectrograms and MFCCs, which are widely used in speech recognition applications. MFCCs (Mel-frequency cepstral coefficients) offer a compact representation of the power spectrum of an audio signal and are commonly used in speech signal modeling due to their ability to capture essential characteristics of the frequency spectrum shape (Davis and Mermelstein, 1980).

2.3 Speech Recognition

Speech recognition is a crucial step in the audio-based geolocation process, as it involves converting the captured audio into usable text. For this task, we use the SpeechRecognition library in Python, which provides an interface to several speech recognition services, including the previously mentioned Google Web Speech API. The choice of Google Web Speech API is due to its high accuracy and support for multiple languages, which is essential to ensure the system's flexibility and accessibility to a diverse audience.

2.3.1 SpeechRecognition Library

The SpeechRecognition library is widely used for performing speech recognition tasks in Python due to its simplicity and effectiveness. It supports various speech recognition engines, including Google Web Speech API, Microsoft Bing Voice Recognition, and others.

To use the SpeechRecognition library, we first capture audio using a microphone or load an existing audio file. The captured audio is then processed and sent to the selected speech recognition service for transcription.

The accuracy of the Google Web Speech API is one of the main reasons for its selection. Comparative studies show that the Google Web Speech API has a high accuracy rate in various speech recognition scenarios, making it suitable for applications requiring high precision (Nassif et al., 2019). Additionally, support for multiple languages is crucial for the system's flexibility, allowing users from different regions and languages to use the application without language barriers. The multi-language support is implemented in the SpeechRecognition library through the language parameter (Natal, Shires and Jägenstedt, 2020).

The configuration of the SpeechRecognition library ensures that audio is captured and processed efficiently and accurately. The main steps involved are:

- a) Recognizer Initialization: A Recognizer object is initialized to manage the speech recognition operations.
- b) Audio Capture: Audio is captured either from a file or directly from a microphone. In the case of files, AudioFile is used to load the audio.
- c) Audio Processing: The audio is processed for normalization and noise reduction, if necessary, to improve the accuracy of the recognition.
- d) Transcription: The processed audio is sent to the Web Speech API, which returns the transcription in text format. The system handles exceptions to ensure that errors, such as poor connectivity or unrecognized speech, are managed appropriately.

2.4 Geocoding

Geocoding is the process of transforming textual descriptions of locations into geographic coordinates (latitude and longitude), enabling the visual representation of these locations on an interactive map. After the audio is transcribed into text, the geopy library is used to perform the geocoding.

The geopy library facilitates this process, as well as other geospatial operations like distance calculations. For this project, we specifically used the Nominatim service from OpenStreetMap, which is a reliable option for geocoding due to its accuracy and global coverage. Nominatim converts addresses, place names, and other geographic descriptors into latitude and longitude coordinates. It is free to use and relies on a constantly updated database maintained by OpenStreetMap contributors, making it a highly accurate and dependable geocoding solution (Mooney and Corcoran, 2012; Juhász and Hochmair, 2016).

2.5 Visualization

For the visualization component, a web server was implemented using Flask, a microframework for Python that allows the creation of lightweight and efficient web applications. Flask is widely used due to its simplicity and flexibility, enabling rapid development of scalable web applications (Grinberg, 2018).

Flask was chosen for its ability to create web servers that can handle HTTP requests and render HTML pages. A basic implementation of a Flask server for visualizing geocoded data

involves defining routes that respond to different URLs and rendering HTML templates (Grinberg, 2018).

The `render_template_string` function in Flask allows rendering HTML templates from strings, enabling the dynamic insertion of data into the HTML. This functionality allows the creation of dynamic web interfaces, where content can be updated in real time as context variables change. The `request` module in Flask provides access to HTTP request data, allowing for the manipulation of parameters passed via URL. This module facilitates interaction between the client and server, enabling data to be sent and received efficiently and securely (Grinberg, 2018).

The `make_server` function is part of the Werkzeug library and provides a robust foundation for creating WSGI (Web Server Gateway Interface) servers. This functionality is essential for running web applications in Python, ensuring compatibility and effective communication between the server and the application (Ronacher, 2019). The `threading` library allows the simultaneous execution of multiple threads. This capability is crucial for creating web servers that can handle multiple requests concurrently, improving the performance and responsiveness of the application (Downey, 2008).

The `request` module in Flask offers comprehensive access to HTTP request data, making it possible to efficiently manipulate parameters passed via URL. This capability is critical for client-server interaction, allowing for the secure sending and receiving of data. Sinha (2017) highlights the importance of handling HTTP requests in web development, ensuring smooth communication between the frontend and backend. Flask simplifies this interaction by supporting multiple request methods (e.g., GET, POST), enabling the creation of responsive endpoints that meet various application needs.

The Python standard library `threading` allows the execution of multiple threads simultaneously, which is essential for web servers to handle concurrent requests, improving the application's performance and responsiveness. Thread execution in Python is managed by creating `Thread` objects, where each thread can execute a specific function independently. The `threading` module also provides synchronization mechanisms like locks, events, and conditions, which are crucial for avoiding race conditions and ensuring the integrity of shared data (Python Software Foundation, 2023).

The `IPython.display` library is used to display interactive results in IPython environments such as Jupyter Notebooks. This tool is particularly useful for visualizing data and presenting results interactively and dynamically. It allows the incorporation of graphs, tables, and other visual elements directly into notebooks, making the process of data interaction and analysis more intuitive and effective (Pérez and Granger, 2007).

The `app` instance represents the Flask application. This object is essential as it configures the application, defines routes, and manages the application's lifecycle. The `render_page` function is responsible for generating the dynamic HTML page. This function uses the template string technique to embed dynamic data (latitude, longitude, and address) into the HTML. The `Leaflet.js` library, a lightweight JavaScript library, was used for rendering OpenStreetMap maps due to its simplicity and efficiency (Chilton, 2014). The Web Speech API enables voice synthesis, allowing text to be read aloud, making it useful for accessibility applications (Natal; Shires and Jägenstedt, 2020).

The main route of the web application is defined by the `index` function. This function extracts latitude, longitude, and address parameters from the URL and uses them to render the page with the interactive map.

The `ServerThread` class inherits from the `Thread` class of the `threading` library and is used to run the Flask server in a separate thread. This allows the server to handle multiple requests

simultaneously, improving the responsiveness and performance of the web application (Downey, 2008). The `start_server` and `stop_server` functions manage the start-up and shutdown of the Flask server. The `start_server` function starts the server on the specified port (`port=6060`), checking if a server is already running, while the `stop_server` function stops the server if it is running, freeing up allocated resources.

2.6 User Interface Development

The user interface (UI) is a vital part of this application, as it serves as the point of interaction between the user and the application. The UI is designed to be intuitive and interactive, providing a seamless and satisfying user experience. This is achieved through a combination of visual and functional elements that guide the user through each step of the geolocation process.

The interface was developed using a combination of HTML (HyperText Markup Language), CSS (Cascading Style Sheets), and JavaScript. HTML defines the structure of the UI elements, including buttons, instructional text, and the map container, while CSS applies specific visual styles to improve the aesthetics and usability of the interface (W3Schools, 2023). JavaScript was chosen as the programming language to add interactive functionalities to the interface. Its DOM (Document Object Model) manipulation capabilities allow for dynamic updates and immediate responses to user actions (Mdn Web Docs, 2023). This approach is based on best practices in UI design, which emphasize user accessibility and usability (Nielsen, 1993).

As previously mentioned, buttons were implemented using HTML and styled with CSS to ensure they are intuitive and visually prominent.

JavaScript functions control the activation and deactivation of voice commands, using the browser's Speech Synthesis API, as mentioned earlier. The Leaflet.js library is used to create and manipulate the interactive map, as well as to add a marker at the geocoded position.

3. Results and Discussions

This chapter presents the results and discussions regarding the implementation of an interactive geolocation application developed in the Google Colaboratory environment.

The first message displayed to the user instructs them to speak the name of the city, state, and/or country they wish to geolocate, slowly and clearly. This message is shown in green, while another message, indicating "ready to record," is displayed in purple, signaling that the system is prepared to start recording. These visual cues play a crucial role in guiding the user through the interaction, ensuring that they understand when the system is actively listening and when it is ready to process the voice input. This step is critical to ensure that the captured audio is clear and comprehensible for the subsequent speech recognition stage. The use of JavaScript and the Web Speech API enables the system to detect specific voice commands to start and stop recording, as indicated by the colors and states of the interface (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - Message informing the user to speak slowly the name of the City, State, and/or Country they want to Geolocate and that is Ready to Start Recording

When the start command is recognized, the interface changes to indicate that recording is in progress. The message "Command recognized: starting recording" in red confirms that the command was correctly detected. The message "Recording..." in purple confirms that the recording is in progress.

This visual feedback is essential for the user to confirm that their input has been recognized, enhancing the system's usability. The audio is recorded in `.webm` format for future conversion to a more appropriate format. FIGURE 2, below, illustrates the result of this part of the code.

Figure 2 - Message Informing the user that the command to Start Recording has been Recognized and that recording has Started.

If the voice command is not recognized, the interface displays a red message asking the user to repeat the command. This is crucial to ensure that only valid commands are processed, preventing unwanted recordings or errors. The implementation of this logic enhances the system's robustness, giving the user a second chance to correct potential pronunciation errors or environmental noise. FIGURE 3, below, illustrates the result of this part of the code.

Figure 3 - Message informing the user that the command to start recording was not recognized and asking to say one of the commands to start or stop recording.

After recording, the audio is saved in `.webm` format. If a previous audio file exists, it is automatically overwritten. This approach simplifies file management and prevents unnecessary data accumulation. The `.webm` format was chosen due to its compatibility with modern browsers, ensuring that the audio can be processed in subsequent steps. After recording, the audio is converted to `.wav` using the `ffmpeg` library, and the details of this process are displayed to the user on the screen.

Next, the audio is transcribed using the Web Speech API and the SpeechRecognition interface, with the transcription in the recognized language, along with the confirmation of the geocoded location and its respective latitude and longitude. FIGURE 4, FIGURE 5, and FIGURE 6 illustrate the results of this part of the code, respectively.

Figure 4 - Message informing the user that the audio has been recorded and saved in `.webm` format. If a previous audio exists, it is automatically overwritten and the previous audio is removed.

```

ffmpeg version 4.4.2-0ubuntu22.04.1 Copyright (c) 2000-2021 the FFmpeg developers
built with gcc 11 (Ubuntu 11.2.0-9ubuntu2)
configuration: --prefix=/usr --extra-version=0ubuntu22.04.1 --toolchain=hardened --libdir=/usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu
libavutil 58. 76.100 / 58. 76.100
libavcodec 58.134.100 / 58.134.100
libavformat 58. 76.100 / 58. 76.100
libavdevice 58. 13.100 / 58. 13.100
libavfilter 7.110.100 / 7.110.100
libbswap 5.  9.100 / 5.  9.100
libresample 3.  9.100 / 3.  9.100
libpostproc 55.  9.100 / 55.  9.100
input #0, matroska_webm, from 'audio.webm':
Metadata:
  encoder      : Chrome
  Duration: N/A, start: 0.000000, bitrate: N/A
  Stream #0:0(eng): Audio: opus, 48000 Hz, mono, fltp (default)
Stream mapping:
  Stream #0:0 -> #0:0 (opus (native) -> pcm_s16le (native))
Press [q] to stop, [?] for help
output #0, wav, to 'audio.wav':
Metadata:
  ISFT        : Lavf58.76.100
  Stream #0:0(eng): Audio: pcm_s16le ([1][0][0] / 0x0001), 48000 Hz, mono, s16, 768 kb/s (default)
Metadata:
  encoder      : Lavc58.134.100 pcm_s16le
  size        : 5468 time=00:00:00.75 bitrate= 77.2 kb/s/s speed= 240x
video:0kB audio:5468B subtitle:0kB other streams:0kB global headers:0kB muxing overhead: 0.013960%
    
```

Figure 5 - Conversion of input audio file from .webm format (1) to output audio file in .wav format (2) using the ffmpeg library.

```

▶ 000/000
Trying to recognize speech for pt-BR: Curitiba Paraná Brasil
Location: Curitiba, Região Geográfica Imediata de Curitiba, Região Metropolitan de Curitiba, Região Geográfica Intermediária de Curitiba, Paraná, Região Sul, Brasil
Latitude: -25.423091
Longitude: -49.272728
    
```

Figure 6 - Audio has been recorded and saved in '.webm' format. recognition of the language in which the city, state, and/or country was spoken. transcription of the recorded audio.

The following figures (FIGURE 7 and FIGURE 8) show the interface for visualizing geocoded locations using the Nominatim library. The displayed information includes the city, region, country, latitude, and longitude. The interactive map allows the user to view and interact with the located position, adjusting the zoom level and receiving a voice message indicating the current zoom level of the map. As seen in the code, the default zoom level is set to 13.

You can observe how the buttons for interaction are highlighted and visible to the user. Another highlight is the blue marker placed on the geolocated city. FIGURE 7 and FIGURE 8, respectively, illustrate the result of this part of the code.

Figure 7 - Interface visualization of a geolocation. information from the nominatim library (city, immediate geographical region, intermediate geographical region, state, region, country, latitude, and longitude) about the found location can be observed.

Figure 8 - Examples of the interface visualization for some locations (Curitiba, London, and Barcelona). highlight on the user interaction buttons and the blue marker placed on the geolocated city.

Once the user clicks the "Disable voice reading" or "Stop voice reading" buttons, confirmation messages are displayed, indicating that the voice reading has been disabled or stopped, as shown below. These messages are important to ensure that the user knows their actions have been executed by the system. FIGURE 9 and FIGURE 10, respectively, illustrate the result of this part of the code.

Figure 9 - Message displayed when the user clicks the 'Disable Voice Reading' button.

Figure 10 - Message displayed when the user clicks the 'stop voice reading' button.

4. Final Considerations and Recommendations

Various innovations in technologies like voice recognition and natural language processing are transforming how we interact with complex data and systems. The ability to identify the exact location of a device or person in real-time, especially in applications such as navigation and emergency services, has revolutionized our interactions with the environment. This study aligns with the "Digital Earth" vision, emphasizing the importance of making geospatial data accessible and usable by a wide range of users.

The development of an audio-based geolocation application in the Google Colaboratory environment, as detailed in the previous chapters, demonstrates the feasibility and effectiveness of integrating voice recognition, natural language processing, and geocoding technologies. As a result, the initial objective was achieved, and the research question that drove this study has been answered.

This work presented several tools and technologies that can contribute to significant advancements in the field of human-computer interaction, offering an intuitive and accessible interface for users of different levels of technical proficiency within the Google Colaboratory environment.

Future research could explore the integration of other emerging technologies, such as Augmented Reality, to further enhance interaction and the accuracy of geolocation applications. Additionally, studies could investigate applying this system in different contexts, such as education, urban planning, and emergency management, to assess its impact and usefulness in real-world scenarios.

Further recommendations include expanding the voice reading and interaction functions with the map, eliminating the need for any peripherals for interaction. This could involve implementing bounding boxes to enable voice-based location identification, improving the system's precision and efficiency. Moreover, it is recommended to explore and implement solutions that do not rely on JavaScript and Flask, seeking alternatives that could offer simpler and more direct integration with the tools and technologies used. Another area for improvement is adapting the system to better understand Brazilian city names when the primary language is set to 'en-US', enhancing speech recognition accuracy in multilingual contexts.

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